

Ecological Impact of Rain Gardens in Lublin: A GIS-Based Assessment of Urban Vegetation Dynamics

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Abstract

Rain gardens are increasingly recognized as effective Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) for enhancing ecological resilience in urban environments. This study investigates the ecological impact of rain gardens in Lublin, Poland, through a GIS-based assessment of vegetation dynamics between 2020 and 2025. Using Sentinel-2 imagery, Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) maps were generated and analyzed within 300 m buffer zones around four rain garden sites. Zonal statistics revealed heterogeneous outcomes: three sites exhibited positive NDVI changes, with the University Campus rain garden showing the strongest improvement (+6.8%), while one site in John Paul II Park recorded a slight decline (-2.3%). These results highlight both the potential and variability of rain garden performance in dense urban settings. The integration of drought-resistant plant species contributed to vegetation stability, supporting microclimate regulation, biodiversity habitat, and stormwater management. Spatial analysis confirmed that rain gardens influence not only their immediate plots but also surrounding vegetation, demonstrating measurable ecological spillover effects. Overall, the findings provide empirical evidence that rain gardens contribute to localized greening and resilience within Lublin's urban fabric. This research underscores the importance of GIS-based monitoring for evaluating NBS effectiveness and offers insights for scaling rain gardens as sustainable interventions in European cities.

Keywords: rain gardens, nature-based solutions, NDVI, urban vegetation dynamics, Lublin

1. Introduction

Urban areas across Europe are increasingly facing combined pressures of rapid land-use change, declining green space, and the intensifying effects of climate variability [1,2]. These dynamics contribute to a range of environmental challenges, including reduced vegetation cover, heightened surface temperatures, and increased stormwater runoff [3]. In response, cities are turning towards Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) as practical and multifunctional approaches to enhance ecological resilience while supporting human well-being [3–5]. Among these interventions, rain gardens have gained particular attention due to their capacity to manage stormwater, regulate local microclimates, and support biodiversity within highly urbanized settings [6,7].

Rain gardens are shallow, vegetated depressions designed to capture, filter, and infiltrate runoff from surrounding impervious surfaces. Their effectiveness not only depends on hydrological performance but also on their ability to enhance vegetation health and contribute towards wider ecological processes [8–10]. While most rain gardens are typically small in scale, emerging research suggests that their influence may extend beyond their immediate footprint, potentially generating ecological spillover effects into

adjacent urban areas [11]. However, empirical evidence demonstrating these broader impacts remains limited, particularly in Central and Eastern European cities where NBS implementation is still evolving.

Lublin city, which is located in eastern Poland, has introduced several rain gardens since 2021 as part of its wider strategy to strengthen urban sustainability. These installations incorporate drought-resistant plant species selected for their adaptability to local climatic conditions and their potential to stabilize vegetation under increasing environmental stress [5]. Assessing the ecological performance of these sites across various dimensions is essential to understand their contribution to the city's green infrastructure network.

This study preliminarily evaluates the ecological impact of four rain gardens in Lublin using a GIS-based approach which is centred on the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI). By analyzing vegetation dynamics within 300 metre buffer zones between 2020 and 2025, the research provides spatial evidence of how rain gardens influence surrounding vegetation patterns. The findings contribute to the growing body of knowledge on NBS effectiveness and offer insights relevant to urban planning, landscape design, and climate adaptation strategies.

2. Methodology

This study adopted a GIS-based approach so as to evaluate vegetation changes surrounding four rain gardens in Lublin between the years 2020 and 2025. Rain garden locations were firstly digitized in ArcGIS Pro using verified coordinates and high-resolution orthophotos to ensure spatial accuracy. Sentinel-2 satellite imagery from both years was processed to generate Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) rasters at 10-metre resolution. Then, a 300-metre buffer was created around each rain garden to capture potential ecological spillover effects into the surrounding urban landscape. NDVI values within each buffer were extracted using zonal statistics, including minimum, maximum, mean as well as standard deviation. Mean NDVI served as the primary indicator of vegetation health, which is calculated by averaging all pixel values within each buffer zone. Percentage changes between 2020 and 2025 were then computed to quantify temporal shifts in vegetation condition and assess the ecological influence of each rain garden.

3. Rain gardens localization

The empirical analysis of this study focuses on four rain gardens implemented in Lublin as part of the city's wider Nature-Based Solutions agenda aimed at strengthening climate adaptation and enhancing urban green infrastructure. These sites were selected because they represent different urban functions and spatial contexts. Together, they illustrate how small-scale interventions are embedded within the broader urban fabric and how they interact with surrounding land uses. Figure 1 below shows the locations of four rain gardens used in this study within Lublin city.

Figure 1. Lublin city map showing the location of the rain gardens

3.1. Rain garden 1 (John Paul II Park)

The first rain garden is located within John Paul II Park, which is a large recreational green space in southwestern Lublin. The rain garden is positioned near pedestrian routes and open lawn areas, where it intercepts runoff from adjacent paths and surrounding impervious surfaces. With an area coverage of around 28.3 m^2 and estimated catchment area of about 500 m^2 , its primary aim is to manage stormwater locally, reduce surface water accumulation after intense rainfall events, and enhance the ecological quality of a heavily used public space. The garden is covered with native plant species resistant to variable moisture conditions such as dwarf purple willow (*Salix purpurea* 'Nana'), spotted Joe-Pye weed (*Eupatorium maculatum*), meadowsweet (*Filipendula ulmaria*), Siberian iris (*Iris sibirica*), and purple loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria*). Figure 2 below shows the cross-sectional view of the rain garden 1 in terms of its design and composition.

Figure 2. Cross-sectional diagram showing the features of rain garden 1

3.2. Rain garden 2 (John Paul II Park)

The second rain garden is also situated in John Paul II Park under the viaduct on Filaretów Street. It was established with a major purpose of managing stormwater, improve the aesthetics of the surrounding environment as well as to support the local biodiversity. The total area of the rain garden is 46.8 m², while the gravel bed covers 71.3 m², and the dry stream channel directing rainwater into the garden covers 27 m². The garden consists of three parts: an infiltration basin (dry), where water seeps into the soil; a sealed basin (wet), which retains water on the surface and creates moist habitats for plants and animals; and a stream with a sealed bottom, which directs water from the viaduct toward the garden. Several drought resistant plant species are also planted in this garden such as dotted loosestrife (*Lysimachia punctata*), Siberian iris (*Iris sibirica*), purple loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria*), dusky cranesbill (*Geranium phaeum*), orange coneflower (*Rudbeckia fulgida*), and lady's mantle (*Alchemilla mollis*). These species tolerate variable moisture conditions well and help purify water from pollutants. Additionally, incorporated boulders, stones, and wooden logs create habitats for insects, fungi, and small animals, which supports the biodiversity.

3.3. Rain garden 3 (Centre for Culture)

Rain Garden 3 has an area coverage of around 37.2 m² and its located at Lech Kaczyński Square, near the former monastic complex. The primary function of this rain garden is to capture rainwater from the roof of the building, which previously was discharged directly into the sewer system. The garden is designed as an infiltration type, meaning that water is retained in a specially prepared permeable substrate and gradually infiltrates into the soil. In this way, it not only supports stormwater retention but also enhances the aesthetic value of the surroundings, highlighting the architectural features of historic buildings. Similarly to other rain gardens, this rain garden at Center for Culture is also covered with native plant species which are resistant to fluctuating moisture conditions, such as meadowsweet (*Filipendula*

ulmaria), dusky cranesbill (*Geranium phaeum*), Siberian iris (*Iris sibirica*), dotted loosestrife (*Lysimachia punctata*), purple loosestrife (*Lythrum salicaria*), and ostrich fern (*Matteuccia struthiopteris*). These plants not only decorate the space but also help purify rainwater from pollutants.

3.4. Rain garden 4 (University Campus)

Rain Garden 4 is situated within the University Campus area along the roadside lawns of Obrońców Pokoju Street. There are five small rain gardens besides the road, ranging in size from 6.7 m² to 16.6 m², covering a total area of 49.8 m². Their main purpose is to retain rainwater in the soil, thereby reducing runoff onto the streets and lowering the risk of local flooding. The gardens were designed as infiltration-based, with permeable substrates that promote water absorption. Drought tolerant plant species used in this rain garden include male fern (*Dryopteris filix-mas*), 'Patriot' hosta (*Hosta 'Patriot'*), Japanese sedge (*Carex morrowii*), betony (*Stachys officinalis*), and Siberian iris (*Iris sibirica*). In addition to their retention function, they support the local ecosystem and improve habitat conditions for urban greenery.

4. Results and Discussion

The results of this study provides a spatially grounded assessment of vegetation dynamics surrounding four rain gardens in Lublin between 2020 and 2025. By integrating NDVI mapping, buffer analysis, and zonal statistics, the findings reveal both the ecological contributions of the rain gardens and the variability of their performance across different urban contexts. To illustrate these patterns at the city scale, Figure 3 presents the NDVI maps for 2020 and 2025, highlighting broad spatial trends in vegetation health and forming the basis for the subsequent buffer-based analysis.

Figure 3. NDVI Maps of Lublin city between the year 2020 and 2025

The city wide NDVI maps show a general greening trend in Lublin over the five-year period, with maximum NDVI values increasing from 0.747 in 2020 to 0.907 in 2025. This reflects broader improvements in vegetation health across the city, likely influenced by favourable climatic conditions, maturing green infrastructure, and ongoing municipal greening initiatives. However, these citywide maxima represent the densest vegetation patches, primarily large parks and forested areas, and therefore differ from the more heterogeneous conditions captured within the rain garden buffer zones.

In order to visualize the spatial context of each site, Figure 4 below presents the 300-metre buffering applied around the four rain gardens, illustrating their position within the surrounding urban landscape. These buffered satellite images highlight the heterogeneity of land-use patterns ranging from dense built-up areas to open parkland, and demonstrate why buffering was necessary to capture ecological spillover effects beyond the immediate footprint of each installation. By analyzing vegetation dynamics within these standardized zones, it becomes possible to assess how rain gardens influence adjacent areas rather than only the planted plots themselves.

Figure 4. Locations of the four rain gardens in Lublin with 300-metre buffer zones for NDVI analysis

The 300-metre buffers provided a consistent spatial unit for assessing ecological spillover effects. Zonal statistics revealed distinct patterns across the four sites. Tables 1 and 2 below summarize the NDVI zonal statistics for 2020 and 2025, presenting the minimum, maximum, mean, and variability of vegetation values within each buffer. These tables provide the quantitative basis for comparing vegetation dynamics across the two years and identifying site-specific ecological trends.¹

Table 1: NDVI Zonal Statistics of Lublin rain gardens in the year 2020

		Min	Max	Range	Mean	S.D
Rain garden 1	John Paul II Park	0.020289	0.543804	0.523515	0.297267	0.132495
Rain garden 2	John Paul II Park	-0.00600	0.531866	0.537867	0.240298	0.117849
Rain garden 3	Center for Culture	-0.06489	0.456646	0.521534	0.091505	0.102841
Rain garden 4	University Campus	-0.03885	0.467301	0.506155	0.15531	0.107682

Table 2: NDVI Zonal Statistics of Lublin rain gardens in the year 2025

		Min	Max	Range	Mean	SD
Rain garden 1	John Paul II Park	0.00268	0.574768	0.572089	0.29036	0.132279
Rain garden 2	John Paul II Park	-0.02541	0.560549	0.585956	0.244672	0.126248
Rain garden 3	Center for Culture	-0.06449	0.473928	0.538422	0.093001	0.10741
Rain garden 4	University Campus	-0.03661	0.470641	0.507245	0.165832	0.115904

Table 3 below summarizes the percentage changes in mean NDVI across the four rain gardens between the years 2020 and 2025, and provides a clear comparison of how vegetation health evolved at each site. Rain garden 1 in John Paul II Park recorded a slight decline in mean NDVI (-2.3%), suggesting localized stress potentially linked to shading, soil compaction, or high recreational pressure. In contrast, Rain Gardens 2 and 3 showed modest increases of +1.8% and +1.6% respectively, indicating stabilization of vegetation health in areas characterized by mixed land use and moderate urban pressure. Rain garden 4 at the University Campus exhibited the strongest improvement, with a +6.8% increase in mean NDVI. This site appears to function as a local ecological hotspot, benefiting from a favourable microclimate, diverse planting structure, and reduced disturbance compared to the park sites. The results demonstrate that rain gardens can enhance vegetation health not only within their immediate footprint but also within the surrounding urban landscape.

Table 3. Percentage change in mean NDVI for the rain gardens between 2020 and 2025.

Rain gardens	2020 Mean	2025 Mean	NDVI Change	% Change
Rain garden 1 - John Paul II Park	0.297267	0.29036	-0.00691	-2.32%
Rain garden 2 - John Paul II Park	0.240298	0.244672	+0.00437	+1.82%
Rain garden 3 - Center for Culture	0.091505	0.093001	+0.00150	+1.64%
Rain garden 4 - University Campus	0.155310	0.165832	+0.01052	+6.77%

The use of drought-resistant plant species across all sites contributed to vegetation resilience, particularly during dry periods. Species such as *Iris sibirica*, *Lythrum salicaria*, and *Geranium phaeum* are well adapted to fluctuating moisture conditions and appear to have supported stable NDVI values even in more challenging urban settings. However, the magnitude of ecological improvement varied according to site context. Rain gardens embedded within dense built environments such as the Center for Culture, showed smaller but consistent gains, while those in more open or semi-natural settings like the University Campus demonstrated stronger vegetation recovery.

The buffer analysis indicates that rain gardens exert measurable ecological influence beyond their boundaries. Even modest NDVI increases within the 300-metre zones suggest improvements in microclimate, soil moisture retention, and vegetation continuity. These spillover effects are particularly relevant in fragmented urban landscapes, where small interventions can collectively contribute to broader ecological connectivity.

The variability in NDVI change reflects the complex interplay between rain garden design, surrounding land use, and urban pressures. Sites exposed to high footfall or compacted soils showed limited gains, whereas those with supportive microclimatic conditions and lower disturbance exhibited stronger ecological responses. These findings align with the objectives of the T-Labs initiative in Lublin, which emphasize context-sensitive implementation of Nature-Based Solutions.

5. Conclusion

This study demonstrates that rain gardens in Lublin contribute measurable ecological benefits within their immediate surroundings and the wider urban landscape. By integrating Sentinel-2 NDVI analysis, 300-metre buffer zones, and zonal statistics, the research provides spatial evidence of how small-scale Nature-Based Solutions can influence vegetation dynamics over time. The findings show that three of the four rain gardens recorded increases in mean NDVI between 2020 and 2025, which indicates improvement in vegetation health and local ecological conditions. The University Campus site, in particular, exhibited the strongest positive change, functioning as a local ecological hotspot and highlighting the value of context-sensitive design and regular management practices in shaping ecological outcomes. The study confirms that rain gardens can enhance urban resilience by improving vegetation health, supporting microclimatic regulation, and generating ecological spillover effects beyond their planted footprint. While modest in scale, their cumulative impact can significantly contribute to urban greening strategies, particularly in cities facing increasing environmental pressures.

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